

very kindly providing uv and ir spectra respectively. Authors are also grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship to one to them (N.J.S.).

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Allylation of 2, 4-dihydroxyphenylbenzylketone (I) gave 4-allyloxy derivative(II) which was condensed with diethyl carbonate to give 7-allyloxy-4-hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin(III) which on methylation with dimethylsulphate gave 7-allyloxy-4-methoxy-3-phenylcoumarin(IV). (IV), on Claisen migration gave two products, one soluble in NaHCO₃ solution, 8-allyl-4-7-dihydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin(V) and the other soluble in sodium hydroxide solution, 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-phenylcoumarin(VI). The structure of (VI) was confirmed by NMR spectrum which showed two doublets at δ 6.85 and δ 7.60 for two protons at C-6 and C-5 respectively which confirmed that the allyl migration has taken place at C-8 and not at C-6. The Claisen migration of 7-hydroxycoumarins is regiospecifically taking place at position-8 and this has been observed earlier by Trivedi *et al*⁹ and Seshadri *et al*⁸. The products (V) and (VI) on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2, 3-dihydro-7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo (2, 3-h)benzopyran(VII). Demethylation of (VI) occurred during cyclisation. (VII) on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal gave 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(2, 3-h) benzopyran (VIII).

Synthesis of 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-2, 3-dihydro-5-oxo-5H-furo(2, 3-h)benzopyran(XV) and 2, 9-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-phenyl-7-oxo-7H-furo(3, 2-g)benzopyran(XXIII) were achieved by carrying out the above series of reactions on 2, 4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxyphenylbenzylketone(IX) and 2, 4-dihydroxy - 3 - methylphenylbenzylketone (XVI) respectively.

Studies in the Synthesis of Furocoumarins :
Part XXV*

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Manuscript received 24 September 1979, revised 29 September 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

I R₁=R₂=R₃=H; II R₁=R₂=H, R₃=-CH₂CH=CH₂; IX R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃; X R₁=H; R₂=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₃=OCH₃; XVI R₁=CH₃; R₂=R₃=H and XVII R₁=CH₃; R₂=CH₂-CH=CH₂; R₃=H

4-HYDROXY-3-PHENYLCOUMARIN derivatives are found to occur in nature and belong to the groups of isoflavonoids¹. Robustic acid, robustin, scandenin and wedelolactone are few examples of this type. In our previous work, we have reported the synthesis of furocoumarins of angelicin and psoralene²⁻⁶ types, we report here the synthesis of 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo (2, 3-h) benzopyran(VIII), 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-2, 3-dihydro-5-oxo-5H-furo (2, 3-h)benzopyran(XV) and 2, 9-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-phenyl-7-oxo-7H-furo-(3, 2-g)benzopyran (XXIV).

III R₁=R₂=R₄=R₅=H; R₃=-CH₂CH=CH₂; IV R₁=R₂=R₃=H; R₄=-CH₂CH=CH₂; R₅=H; V R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=R₄=R₅=H; VI R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=R₄=H; R₅=CH₃; XI R₁=R₂=R₄=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₅=CH₃; R₆=OCH₃; XII R₁=R₂=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₄=CH₃; R₅=OCH₃; XIII R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=R₄=H; R₅=OCH₃; XIV R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=H; R₄=CH₃; R₅=OCH₃; XVIII R₁=CH₃; R₂=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₃=R₄=R₅=H; XIX R₁=R₂=CH₃; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₄=R₅=H; XX R₁=CH₃; R₂=R₃=R₄=H; R₅=CH₂CH=CH₂ and XXI R₁=R₂=CH₃; R₃=R₄=H; R₅=CH₂CH=CH₂

* Part XXIV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 56.

NOTES

VII $R_1=R_2=H$; 2,3-Dihydro; VIII: $R_1=R_2=H$; 2,2-Dehydro and XV $R_1=H$; $R_2=OOH_3$; 2,3-Dihydro

XXII 2,3-Dihydro and XXIII 2,3-Dehydro

Experimental

General procedure for the synthesis of allyloxy-2-hydroxy-phenylbenzylketone derivatives (II, X, XVII):

A mixture of I, IX or XVI 1.0 g), allyl bromide (0.5 ml), acetone (50 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g) was refluxed for 3 hr. The working up of the reaction mixtures gave corresponding oily mono allyloxy derivatives (II, X, XVII).

Allyloxy-3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives (III, XI, XVIII):

A solution of allyloxy-2-hydroxy-phenylbenzylketone derivatives (II, X or XVII) (2 g) in diethyl

carbonate (15 ml) was added slowly to the pulverized sodium (2 g) and heated on a water bath for 10-15 hr. Alcohol was added to destroy unreacted sodium. This on acidification gave corresponding 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives (Table 1).

Methoxy derivatives of coumarins were prepared by refluxing them with dimethyl sulphate in acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

Claisen migration of allyloxy-3-phenylcoumarin derivatives (IV, XII and XIX):

Allyloxy coumarin IV, XII or XIX (2 g) was dissolved in dimethylaniline (15 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 hr. On working up the reaction mixture gave two products in each case (Table 1).

The products V, XIII and XX were soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution. The other products VI, XIV and XXI were soluble in sodium hydroxide solution and their structures were confirmed on the basis of NMR spectra (Table 4).

2-Methyl-2, 3-dihydrofurobenzopyrone derivatives (VII, XV and XXII):

The allyl-3-phenylcoumarin derivative V, XIII or XX (0.5 g) was triturated with sulphuric acid

TABLE I

Coumarin derivatives	Crystallising solvent	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis %			
				Found C	Found H	Required C	Required H
1. III	Chloroform	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	195	73.00	4.93	73.47	4.78
2. Methyl ether of III(IV)	Benzene-petroleum ether	$C_{19}H_{16}O_4$	85-6	73.52	5.61	74.02	5.19
3. V	Methanol	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	193	73.69	4.93	73.47	4.78
4. VI	Alcohol	$C_{16}H_{16}O_4$	191-2	74.22	4.92	74.02	5.19
5. XI	Alcohol	$C_{16}H_{16}O_5$	166-8	71.03	4.89	70.40	4.92
6. Methyl ether of XI (XII)	Benzene-petroleum ether	$C_{20}H_{18}O_5$	110	71.46	5.62	71.00	5.32
7. XIII	Alcohol	$C_{16}H_{16}O_5$	184 (dec.)	71.03	5.26	70.40	4.92
8. XIV	Alcohol	$C_{20}H_{18}O_5$	207-8	71.47	5.34	71.00	5.32
9. XVIII	Benzene-petroleum ether	$C_{19}H_{16}O_4$	212-14	74.49	5.66	74.02	5.19
10. Methyl ether of XVIII (XIX)	Benzene-petroleum ether	$C_{20}H_{18}O_4$	130-1	74.92	6.02	74.53	5.59
11. XX	Benzene-petroleum ether	$C_{16}H_{16}O_4$	174-6	74.22	5.64	74.02	5.19
12. XXI	Benzene-petroleum ether	$C_{20}H_{18}O_4$	215-6	74.42	5.80	74.53	5.59

TABLE 2

	2-Methyl-2,3-dihydrofurobenzopyrone derivatives.	Crystallising solvent	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Analysis %			
					Found C	Found H	Requires C	Requires H
1.	VII	Aqueous alcohol	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ .1/2H ₂ O	224-5	71.80	4.73	71.22	4.95
2.	XV	Ethyl acetate-petroleum ether	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₅ .1/2H ₂ O	212	68.77	5.02	68.46	5.10
3.	XXII	Benzene	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	214-5	73.52	5.67	74.02	5.19

TABLE 3

	2-Methylfurobenzopyrone derivatives	Crystallising solvent	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Analysis %			
					Found C	Found H	Requires C	Requires H
1.	VIII	Ethyl acetate-petroleum ether	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄	208	73.50	4.62	73.97	4.19
2.	XXIII	Alcohol	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	258	74.70	4.66	74.50	4.57

TABLE 4

¹H-NMR spectra* of coumarin derivatives (δ ppm)

Compound	Solvent	C ₃ -ph	C ₄ -OCH ₃	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇ -OH	C ₈ -CH ₂ -CH=CH ₂			C' ₄ -OOH ₂
							-CH ₂ -	-CH ₂	-OH=	
1. VI	CDCl ₃	7.41 (m)	3.52 (s)	7.60 (d)	6.85 (d)	—	3.66 (d)	5.15 (m)	5.95 (m)	—
2. XIV	CDCl ₃	6.98 (d) and 7.40 (d)	3.55 (s)	7.65 (d)	6.82 (d)	—	3.70 (d)	5.20 (m)	6.00 (m)	3.85 (s)

* ¹H-NMR spectrum of 2-methyl-2,3-dihydrofurobenzopyrone

Compound	Solvent	C ₂ -CH ₃	C ₂ -H	C ₃ -H ₂	C ₄ -H	C ₅ -OH	C ₆ -Ph	C ₈ -CH ₃
1. XXII	ODCl ₃	1.53 (d)	5.08 (m)	2.89-3.40 (two q)	7.52 (s)	—	7.47 (m)	2.30 (s)

* ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 90 MHz Spectrometer, using TMS as an internal standard.

IR ν_{max} (nujol) of VI : 3400 cm⁻¹(-OH) and 1680 cm⁻¹(-COO-).

IR ν_{max} (nujol) of XIII : 3400 cm⁻¹(-OH) and 1655 cm⁻¹(-COO-).

IR ν_{max} (nujol) of XIV : 3400 cm⁻¹(-OH) and 1665 cm⁻¹(-COO-).

(5 ml ; 80%) on a water bath for 10 minutes. The reaction mixture on working up gave corresponding 2-methyl-2, 3-dihydrofurobenzopyrone derivatives VII, XV and XXII (Table 2).

These dihydrofurobenzopyrones VII, XV and XXII were also obtained from VI, XIV and XXI respectively by similar reaction with sulphuric acid (5 ml ; 80%).

2-Methylfurobenzopyran derivatives (VIII and XXIII) :

A mixture of 2-methyl-2, 3-dihydrofurobenzopyran derivative VII or XXII (0.5 g), diphenyl ether (10 ml) and palladised charcoal (0.3 g ; 10%) was refluxed for 3 to 5 hr. The solution was cooled and catalyst was removed to obtain dehydrogenated product VIII or XXIII (Table 3). The dihydro product XV could not be dehydrogenated.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. Sukh Dev, Multi-Chem Research Centre, Nandesari, Baroda for NMR spectra and Dr. S. S. Lele for microanalysis of the compounds.

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Studies of Azo Derivatives of 8-Amino-10, 11-Dihydro-5H-Dibenzo (b,e) (1,4)-Diazepin-11-Thione : Part IV

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Manuscript received 16 October 1979, revised 13 October 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

Chart—I

DIAZONIUM salt of 8-amino-10, 11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo (b,e) (1,4)-diazepin-11-thione(I) was condensed with phenol, resorcinol, α - and β -naphthols, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids, separately and azo dyes (II~VII) were obtained.

In dibenzodiazepines, known as potent CNS drugs being used as antihistaminic, spasmolytic, antiparkinson and neuroplegic drugs¹ (Tarpan, Noveril and Clozapine² are some marketed drugs), aryl-azo group has been introduced. Azo dyes are also important class of pharmacological drugs^{2,3}. Diazonium salt of I was condensed at 0-5° with phenol, resorcinol, α - and β -naphthols, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic or 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids separately and the corresponding azo dyes (II~VII) with yellow to red shades were obtained.

Experimental

All the m.p.'s are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord using KBr pellets. The purity of the azo dyes was ascertained by tlc using silica gel G as stationary phase and C₆H₆ : C₂H₅OH : NH₃ (7 : 2 : 1, solvent layer) as mobile phase.

Synthesis of Azo Dyes :

8-p-Hydroxyphenylazo-10,11-Dihydro-11-Thione-5H-Dibenzo (b, e)-1,4-Diazepine-II-Thione :

To the diazotised solution of I* (1.2050 g, 0.05M in 3 ml of conc. HCl, 2.0 ml of acetic acid and 0.8 g of sodium nitrite at 0-5°) alkaline solution of phenol (0.675 g in 5 ml of 10% NaOH) was gradually added with stirring keeping temperature range, 0-5°. The precipitated azo dye was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (II, m.p. 285°, yield 0.9812 g, 56.72%, R_f 0-59).

On similar lines azo dyes (III~VII) were obtained by condensing diazonium salt of I with

TABLE 1

Compound Number	Molecular Formula	Colour	m.p.	R _f	Yield	Visible Range		ir (cm) ⁻¹
						$\lambda_{\max}$	$E_{\max}$	
II	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	Red	285	0.59	56.72	400	11040	3120, 1610, 1575, 1390
III	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	Yellowish Brown	180	0.70	57.52	412	13350	3480, 1620, 1570, 1395
IV	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	Red	130	0.58	58.66	410	11400	3400, 1640, 1550, 1300
V	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	Red	230	0.56	59.83	428	13020	3440, 1600, 1500, 1375
VI	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	Reddish Yellow	250	0.62	55.29	460	11250	3400, 1680, 1570, 1390
VII	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	Yellow	200	0.65	60.92	457	13500	3400, 1640, 1580, 1405

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